

MASSIVE GROWTH OF BANKING TECHNOLOGY WITH THE AID OF 5G TECHNOLOGIES

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ABSTRACT

The advancement in information technology has resulted in explosive growth in banking technology like ATMs, internet banking and mobile banking. Banks which emphasize more on existing customer satisfaction and in attracting new customer have implemented online banking and mobile technology to make banking more convenient, attractive and simple. Computerization, wireless network, ATMS, internet banking and mobile banking can connect any customer of any bank in any branch with a customer in any other bank regardless of time, location or physical boundaries. With the widespread of banking technology, public users or customers could create an account from their smart phone without actually visiting the branch. 5G (Fifth generation wireless systems) is emerging mobile telecommunication standard beyond 4G in terms of speed, bandwidth, data transfer rate and signaling efficiency. Research and analysis of the new technology help in the popularity of the technology among public users. In this paper, we discuss and analyze new banking technology, which includes Digital Deposit Apps, Photo Bill Payment Apps, Smartphone Credit Card Scanners, Electronic Meeting, Advanced ATM Apps and Mobile Payment Apps. The new technologies are analyzed using its advantages, benefits, constraints and disadvantages. Wish this paper could play an active role in actual research of mobile banking technology.

Keywords: Digital Deposit Apps, Photo Bill Payment Apps, Mobile Payment Apps, Electronic Meeting, Smartphone Credit Card Scanners, GoBank.

Introduction:

The topic 'Collection Development' covers a broad range of activities related to the policies and procedures of selection, assessing user needs, evaluation of the present collection, weeding out, and storing parts of the collection and planning for resource sharing. Collection development is not any single activity or group of activities; it is a planning and decision making process.

In recent years, information technologies have advanced to such an extent that their impact on libraries is significant. Particularly, development regarding digital libraries, Internet, electronic publications, CD-ROMs, etc., have forced the librarians to change the way they are now functioning. In this context and also due to the budgetary constraints, librarians are giving importance to 'accessing the other libraries' collection' rather than 'possessing almost all documents' on a given subject. For instance, a number of full text databases are available on Internet. Why then one has to acquire/purchase similar documents? Why can't one access such records and download, if necessary? Once downloaded, such electronic documents, must be classified and catalogued, so that one need not search and download (the same documents again, if and when required. In some cases, however, it may be economic to download again!

An attempt has been made in this paper to discuss the impact of recent advances in IT on collection development.

Impact of CD-ROM:

CD-ROMs are now increasingly being accepted as a standard storage medium based on ISO standards. One CD can store about 650 MB of data. It is estimated that the life-time of a

CO-ROM is almost 100 years-yet to be proved in a real-life situation! There are cases where scratched/damaged CD-ROMs cannot be read by the system and it is practically impossible to acquire them again. More than anything else, it is inexpensive. A large number of CD-ROM databases are available on almost all subjects. Multimedia databases are now increasingly becoming popular. They are the most useful educational tools, especially for the beginners in any subject. No librarian can afford to ignore this development. In the near future, perhaps there is no need for subscribing secondary periodicals in printed media. If CD-ROM databases are subscribed and if they are made available on CD-NET, many can even access them on networks from remote distances. In this environment, librarians can afford to have less shelving space, since bulky volumes are not subscribed; CDs require only least space! Further, complex queries can be searched effectively by Boolean expressions.

Often cost is considered as a major factor to decide whether or not one should subscribe to CD-ROM databases. It is no longer true. Cost is becoming less and less every year. The problem perhaps is of compatibility—hardware and software with its different versions, change so

frequently that one need to worry about its compatibility with new systems. This however has to be tackled by adopting certain international standards. Evaluating CD-ROM databases is yet another task—the simple way is to know:

- How good is its retrieval engine?
- Its coverage by country-wise, language-wise, etc. Does it cover Indian Literature?
- How frequently it is updated?
- Whether it can be replaced, if and when it is damaged or missing?

Impact of internet:

Yet another development in IT applications is the emergence of Internet. Its impact on libraries is considerable. Internet is popularly known as the network of networks. It is being used world-wide for personal and group communication, file transfer and for accessing databases on remote computers.

Information sources on Internet are all stored as computer files of some kind or the other. They have a location on at least one Internet site; may be duplicated at other site (in such a case, it is called a mirror image of the original file). These files on the Internet contain varied materials. Sources like electronic journals, pre-prints, technical reports, numerical and graphical data, software, campus-wide information systems, databases, library catalogues, educational materials, company profiles, patents, standards, information on societies, institutions, associations, etc., are available on Internet. Much of these are 'reference type' in nature. Other resources on Internet can be classified as usenet resources, gopher resources, world wide web resources, WAIS resources, etc.

In this context, libraries may have to review their collection development policy—much of what is available on Internet need not be procured! This however involves a considerable amount of time and cost to conduct a survey of what is available and how long it is available? How much it cost to access—for searching and downloading? This is a difficult task.

Impact of Digital Libraries:

The term digital libraries refers to a new way of carrying out the functions of libraries encompassing new types of electronic information resources, new approaches to acquisition (especially, more access to other libraries' collection and sharing it); new methods of storage and preservation, new approaches to classification and cataloguing, especially of electronic data; intensive use of electronic system and networks and dramatic shifts in intellectual, organisational, and electronic practices. It is also known as a distributed text-based computerised

information system and service. It may have several provisions to access documents, those are of high value, mostly from outside the organisation.

In digital environment, only digital information is disseminated; software is produced locally, and most of the information is obtained by remote accesses; much of this information is less permanent in nature. In these circumstances, it is very difficult for librarians to decide :

- What should be acquired (by downloading), stored and organised?
- Who should do it (most of such information is accessed directly by users, without bringing into the knowledge of librarians)?
- What standards to be followed?
- Users locate and access the information; information is not usually structured; no rules or codes are followed and no one controls the information that is made available.

The data or information may be of different types. To organise the data or information, we require cataloguing practice and it calls for an appropriate data model for organising data with standard font. Specialised technologies are needed for compressing as well as for organising information. These are the major challenges in digital library environment.

Evaluation of Collection:

Evaluation of the library collection is one of the functions of collection development programme. Development of quantitative measures 'to evaluate a collection is usually complicated by the increasing use of CD-ROMs, online services, impact of internet, etc. In traditional methods, the following measures are usually considered for evaluating collection:

- Size of the collection absolute size, size of the rare collection, size of subject, date, language, etc.;
- Number of volumes per user, number of volumes per document circulated, current growth rate, etc.;
- Amount of collection used; and
- Expenditure on collection, etc.

All these measures are inadequate to evaluate a library in the context of recent advances in IT. In addition to the above, the

following measures are equally important in the modern context:

- Availability of CD-ROM databases—number of CD-ROM databases subject-wise, frequency of updation, availability of CD-ROM drives, possibility of is remote access, availability of multimedia databases, etc.
- Access to Internet success rate—how much is really accessed, number of records accessed and downloaded, number of accesses to other electronic publications, response lime, the cost of accessing. Internet and other electronic publications through online services, etc.

It is difficult to collect such data since users can directly access such information through their terminals; librarians may not come lo know such events. Eventually each of the users may have his/her own 'digital library' at very high cost and the library may become virtually non-existent.

One aspect of evaluating collection is keeping track of what is missing and what should be replaced. Replacement decisions may be based on reports of requested items not located and on visual inspection of documents that have been returned. Further, a sample of the collection can be surveyed to establish which subjects are sustaining the greatest losses. The other aspect of evaluation is to identify less used document so that they can be sent to a less expensive building for storing, or can be put into compact storage in a less accessible area of the main library building.

But in the context of IT, it is not that easy to measure the use of electronic records although, it may comparatively be easy to collect the data. It requires entirely a different mission to keep track of frequently used records and organise infrequently used records effectively in a distributed text-based systems. Who has to do this?

All these issues are challenging one in IT environment.

Conclusion:

IT has its impact on collection development. It is necessary to monitor what is available on various networks. It may also be necessary to search frequently such networks and download the relevant records depending upon the local interest. Effective techniques may have to be developed for storing and searching such downloaded data. Since electronic publications, including the CD-ROM databases, are increasingly becoming popular, the policy towards collection development should take care of such trends. The convergence of wireless technologies and the internet is creating a new channel to banking business which inspires the development of value added banking services, the use of smart phones as an access device of banking system functionalities/transactions. With the explosive recent advances in banking technology, customers no longer have to visit a bank branch during normal transactions hours in order to deposit cash, cheque and bill payment or for any other transactions. In 2014 Walmart introduced GoBank for public users or customers to create an account from their smart phone without

actually visiting to the branch [1]. Users from home can deposit a cheque and cash can be credited to their account with the help of wireless electronic check deposit scanning and cashing machine [2].

The International Mobile Telecommunications Advanced (IMT-Advanced) specifies any conditions or requirements for 4G, which includes speed of 100 Mbit/s or more while travelling and 1 Gbit/s while stationary, channel bandwidths of 5-20MHz or sometimes even up to 40MHz, all-IP based packet switching network and able to switch over multiple heterogeneous networks simultaneously. 5G (Fifth generation wireless systems) is emerging mobile telecommunication standard beyond 4G in terms of speed, bandwidth, data transfer rate and signaling efficiency. Next Generation Mobile Network Alliance (NGMN) defines 5G with some requirements, which includes data transfer rate more than 1 Gbit/s and should support tens of thousands of users, up to several lacks of connection simultaneously and spectral and signaling efficiency should be more than 4G [3-4].

In this paper, we discuss and analyze new banking technology, which includes Digital Deposit Apps, Photo Bill Payment Apps, Smartphone Credit Card Scanners, Electronic Meeting, Advanced ATM Apps and Mobile Payment Apps. From Digital Deposit Apps using smart mobile phones the cheque is scanned or digital image of the two sides of cheque have taken and sent to the bank for processing it. Photo Bill Payment Apps works by transmitting digital images of a bill to user's account. The Credit Card Scanners will be attached to smart phones will scan and send the digital information for processing. Loan officer or any other officers of the bank can do direct teleconferencing with a user using an electronic meeting with prior request from the user. The Advanced ATM Apps works on the principle of facial biometric recognition. Mobile Payment Apps helps to make payment for any goods or services. The new technologies are analyzed with its advantages, benefits, constraints and disadvantages.

2. Smart Phone Banking and Communication Technologies

The influences of wireless telecommunication technologies and the internet have made a drastic revolution in banking transactions and services. Smart phone banking is different from ordinary mobile banking because of some unique, special and innovative features of smart phones [5]. With the rising complexity in the e-commerce transactions all over the world, different types of electronic payment appeared in the last few years, out of that few payment methods or techniques are in practice or implemented [6]. As younger consumers are more attracted by smart phone, there is more probability to use mobile banking services like fund transfer, balance enquiry, cheque deposit and bill payments due to its convenience and ubiquitous services [7]. Customers can access their bank accounts with the help of fingerprint reader attached to smart mobile phones.

Cellular communications has brought unparalleled, non comparable rapid changes over the fast few years. By using wireless technologies like WAP smart phone devices can be transformed to sophisticated payment devices that can process both micro and macro payments [8]. 5G technology is going to become a new revolution in mobile wireless communications. Through super core architecture 5G will offer very fast mobile commerce or internet or any other services, with unique standard where all network operators will be connected to one single core, even though they differ in their access technologies [9-11]. 5G is a real wireless world with no more limitations in access technology, connectivity, bandwidth or speed and zone issues [12].

This paper focuses on smart phone banking which involves some advanced features that makes banking transactions anywhere, anytime or ubiquitous. It mainly focuses on six services, which are Digital Deposit Apps, Photo Bill Payment Apps, Smartphone Credit Card Scanners, Electronic Meeting, Advanced ATM Apps and Mobile Payment Apps [1].

3. 5G Enabled Smart Phone Banking

Fifth Generation (5G) Technology not yet been deployed. 5G is a mobile telecommunication standard beyond 4G in terms of speed, bandwidth, data transfer rate and signaling efficiency. The different components of 5G enabled Smart Phone Banking are Digital Deposit Apps, Photo Bill Payment Apps, Smartphone Credit Card Scanners, Electronic Meeting, Advanced ATM Apps and Mobile Payment Apps as shown in figure 1.

Figure 1: 5G Enabled Smart Phone Banking

3. 1. Digital Deposit Apps

Internet technology, wireless mobile communication standards and mobiles Apps made depositing a cheque very simple compared to old fashion paper cheque. In Digital Deposit Apps using Smart Phone users can deposit a cheque and sends two sides of the cheque image or digital scanned image to the bank for processing. In bank cheque will processed as a deposit made by the bank.

3. 2. Photo Bill Payment Apps

In Photo Bill Payment Apps, information's of the bill are transmitted to the respective customer account after taking a digital photograph of the bill. The details of the bill like payment amount, due date and company issuing the bill are collected from the user and bill amount is paid electronically. By setting a proper due date regular bill payment is scheduled using this apps.

3. 3. Smart Phone Credit Card Scanners

Usually credit card is scanned by the scanner or reader owned by the seller. The chances of hacking the password are more in this case. In Smart Phone Credit Card Scanner customer's credit card is scanned by the reader attached to smart phone. The scanner reads the card and specified amount of money is transferred from user's account to payee's account, so that the chance of hacking the password is reduced to an extent.

3.4 Electronic Meeting

In Electronic Meeting teleconferencing with bank teller or loan officer is a new concept going to be introduced in near future. The customer or user has to take prior permission in order to get an appointment with a bank teller or loan officer. Through this service user can open a new account or can apply for a loan or mortgage.

3.5 Advanced ATM Apps

In order to retain the existing customer trust and faith and acquire new customers in ATM transactions, banking institutions should incorporate a stronger security mechanism and thereby overcome from fraudulent transactions or users. In this advanced ATM App as soon as the user stands in front of ATM counter, user facial recognition is captured through facial recognition scanning/identification system attached to ATM machines. Facial recognition are sent to bank server and matched against stored facial recognition. If it matches, then an OTP is sent to user's Smart Phone. When users enter OTP in users Apps through wireless communication, OTP is sent to a bank, again matched with already generated OTP, if matches then ATM machine is opened for the user's transaction.

3.6 Mobile Payment Apps

In Mobile Payment Apps, initially user's credit or debit card information's are loaded into mobile apps. Users might have multiple cards of different banks, all the card information is loaded into mobile apps. Out of multiple choices of card's customer selects any one card from the menu on their Smart Phone and then touches phone to an in-store reader. After this process, payment is processed as like regular credit or debit card transactions.

4. Analysis of 5G Enabled Smart Phone Banking

5G Enabled Smart Phone Banking is analyzed using its advantages, benefits, constraints and disadvantages. Digital Deposit Apps, Photo Bill Payment Apps, Smartphone Credit Card Scanners, Electronic Meeting, Advanced ATM Apps and Mobile Payment Apps six new Smart Phone based banking technologies are studied and analyzed.

Advantages

- Paper less Banking.
- Ubiquitous Transaction facility
- E-slip of the deposited cheque
- Improved Speed, Bandwidth, due to 5G technology
- Automatic bill payment
- Bill payment generates incremental fee revenue
- Smart Phone Credit Card Scanning improves security of customer PIN
- Electronic meeting saves customer time
- In advanced ATMs, difficult to hack/crack the system security
- Improves User Trust over ATM machines
- All bills can be paid without visiting to respective offices
- Easy to use the system, if users are expert in usage of Smart Phone
- 5G Technology makes services more attractive and effective
- Unified standard for wireless communication due to 5G Technology

Benefits

- Global expansion of Smart Phone banking services.
- The ability to obtain a larger customer base due to ubiquitous services.
- The ability to take advantage of the growing popularity of Smart Phone banking through Digital Deposit Apps
- Enhances reputation of the bank by providing fast and secured services to its customer
- Expansion of Smart Phone users
- Banks can able to attract Business people, Software engineers or other tight scheduled customer pool due to their nature of professions.
- Improves consumer reputation of the technology
- High Quality of services are provided due to 5G Technology

Constraints

- Lack of newer technology support
- Possible failure of products due to non-acceptance of customer
- General competitiveness of the banking industry

Disadvantages

- Requirement of high memory and processors at Bank's servers
- Transaction duration time increases.
- Lack of technology support
- Initial investment in technology will be expensive
- Lack of trained staff
- Possibility of misuse of services, especially in electronic meeting
- 5G Technology become more expensive during its initial implementation

5. Conclusion

The advanced wireless communication technologies like 5G will offer a variety of services like mobile internet, mobile commerce and bill payment services with ever pleasant, highly sophisticated and super fast nature. The proposed 5G enabled smart phone banking can offer six services- Digital Deposit Apps, Photo Bill Payment Apps, Smartphone Credit Card Scanners, Electronic Meeting, Advanced ATM Apps and Mobile Payment Apps.

In Digital Deposit Apps the cheque is scanned or digital image of the two sides of the cheque has taken and sent to the bank for processing it. In Photo Bill Payment Apps digital images of a bill are transmitted to user's account. The Credit Card Scanners will be attached to smart phones will scan and send the digital information for processing. Loan officer's can do direct teleconferencing with a user using an electronic meeting with prior request from the user. The Advanced ATM Apps works on the principle of facial biometric recognition. Mobile Payment Apps helps to make payment for any goods or services. The proposed 5G enabled smart phone banking having some characteristics like improved speed, bandwidth, improves the security of customer PIN, saves customer time and improves user trust over ATM machines. Wish this paper could play an active role in actual research of mobile banking technology.

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